

Media Attention and Specialty Choice: Evidence from Healthcare Violence Coverage in Türkiye

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Abstract

This study examines whether the intensity of healthcare violence coverage in Turkish media and online discourse is associated with shifts in medical specialty preferences among physicians, as measured by branch-level minimum scores on the Medical Specialization Examination (TUS). Two text-based treatment proxies are constructed: D_1 , an annual count of Google News articles on healthcare violence (2013–2025), and D_2 , an annual violence proportion derived from a purposively constructed online platform corpus annotated through a multi-stage pipeline combining human annotation and large language model extension. Branches are classified into high-, intermediate-, and low-exposure groups following Dorsey et al. (2003). Spearman correlations and year-level OLS models with exposure-group interaction terms consistently show that higher media intensity is associated with declining minimum scores in high- and intermediate-exposure branches, with high-exposure branches showing an additional decline of approximately one point per standard deviation increase in D_1 relative to low-exposure branches, while low-exposure branches remain unaffected. The D_1 main effect is unstable across trend specifications, but interaction terms are robust to both year dummy and quadratic trend controls, as well as to leave-one-out sensitivity analysis. Results are reported as correlational; causal identification is not claimed.

Keywords: healthcare violence; specialty choice; text as data; media intensity; TUS; Turkey

1. Introduction

Violence against healthcare workers has become an increasingly visible phenomenon in Türkiye’s public discourse. Incidents ranging from verbal harassment to lethal attacks are regularly covered in national media and discussed extensively on social platforms, generating sustained public attention to the deteriorating working conditions of medical professionals. A particularly bleak example occurred in July 2022, when cardiologist Dr. Ekrem Karakaya was shot and killed by a patient’s relative at a hospital in Konya, an incident that triggered nationwide protests among healthcare workers and coincided with a sharp increase in both media coverage and legislative attention to healthcare violence. Survey-based evidence confirms that this exposure has measurable consequences. Eser et al. (2024) document that deteriorating working conditions, including violence risk, are a primary push factor for medical students considering emigration. Moreover, Tek Sevinç et al. (2025) show that healthcare violence coverage directly shapes nursing students’ professional perceptions. Demirbaş et al. (2025) further find that unverified social media reports on healthcare violence negatively affect work motivation and lead healthcare workers to consider changing their field of work. However, whether this sustained media exposure translates into measurable shifts in specialty preferences among practicing physicians remains an empirically open question.

Bo et al. (2020) is the closest reference point in the quantitative literature. They document that newspaper coverage of anti-doctor violence in China significantly reduced enrollment in medical programs. Their identification strategy relies on geographic variation in coverage intensity and exploits a series of high-profile incidents as quasi-natural experiments. The present study adapts this logic to a different decision point: not the choice to enter medicine, but the choice of specialty among practicing physicians in Türkiye. Specialty selection, as revealed through minimum scores on the Medical Specialization Examination (TUS), offers a continuous, nationally comparable indicator of branch-level attractiveness over time. A declining minimum score signals that fewer competitive candidates are choosing a branch, a revealed-preference shift that survey-based studies cannot capture at this scale or temporal resolution. It is important to note, however, that the present study differs from Bo et al. (2020) in a fundamental identification respect: whereas they exploit geographic and incident-level variation as quasi-natural experiments, the identification here rests on 13 annual treatment observations and group-level interaction terms. The framework is the same; the identification is weaker and the findings are reported accordingly as correlational. The branch-level classification follows Dorsey et al. (2003), whose controllable lifestyle framework distinguishes high patient-contact surgical and emergency branches from low-contact lifestyle and basic science branches.

Studying this question requires moving beyond manual content analysis. As Grimmer and Stewart (2013) argue, automated text processing methods are essential for analyzing political and social phenomena at a scale that renders human coding infeasible. In

Türkiye, the relevant discourse spans thousands of news articles and social media entries accumulated over more than a decade, across platforms with distinct audiences and framings. Two complementary text-based proxies are constructed to capture this exposure. The first, D_1 , is an annual count of Google News articles on healthcare violence keywords, validated against official White Code (*Beyaz Kod*) incident notifications, a mandatory reporting system activated when healthcare personnel face threats or violence. The second, D_2 , is derived from a purposively constructed Ekşi Sözlük corpus processed through a multi-stage annotation pipeline combining human coding and large language model extension. Ekşi Sözlük is a participatory Turkish-language platform where registered users collaboratively author entries on any topic; its function is analogous to a combination of Reddit and Wikipedia, serving as a space for social memory and informal public debate. Its educated, urban user base partially overlaps with the population of TUS candidates and practicing physicians (Furman, 2016).

This paper makes three contributions. First, it applies automated text processing methods to construct a longitudinal violence discourse index from Turkish digital media, including a rigorous annotation pipeline with inter-annotator reliability assessment and a post-hoc LLM validation. Second, it links this index to administrative examination data to study specialty-level career responses, extending the Bo et al. (2020) framework to a new institutional and decision-making context. Finally, it demonstrates that the association between media intensity and branch attractiveness is group-specific rather than global. The negative correlation holds for high- and intermediate-exposure branches but not for low-exposure branches, a pattern consistent with a violence-specific deterrence mechanism rather than a general decline in TUS competitiveness.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the outcome variable, treatment proxies, and corpus construction. Section 3 discusses the econometric specifications. Section 4 reports the main findings. Section 5 discusses interpretation and limitations. Section 6 concludes.

2. Data

2.1 Outcome Variable: TUS Minimum Scores

The outcome variable is the minimum score ($score_min$) at the branch level recorded in each session of the Medical Specialization Examination (TUS), administered twice a year by ÖSYM, once in spring and once in autumn. A candidate’s TUS score determines which specialty branches they are eligible to enter; the minimum score for a given branch in a given period therefore reflects the lowest score among candidates who successfully matched to that branch. A declining minimum score in a given branch thus indicates that the branch attracted fewer competitive candidates — in other words, that it became less attractive relative to alternatives, controlling for supply-side expansion captured through the quota control described in Section 3.3. When quota expands, more slots are filled

even by less competitive candidates, the quota control isolates the attractiveness signal from this mechanical effect. This makes *score_min* a revealed-preference indicator of specialty attractiveness at the branch level.

The dataset covers 40 branches across 26 TUS periods from 2013 to 2025, each branch comprising multiple training programs across institutions, yielding a branch-period panel of 46,808 observations after excluding Plastic, Reconstructive and Aesthetic Surgery due to their atypical demand structure. Score data were extracted from official ÖSYM PDF publications using a validated `pdfplumber`-based parser.

The classification adapts the Dorsey et al. (2003) framework, which distinguishes specialties by degree of patient contact and lifestyle controllability, to the full set of TUS branches, extending the original 16-specialty US list to the 40 branches available in Turkish medical education. Branches are classified into three exposure groups. The high-exposure group comprises nine surgical and emergency branches with sustained direct patient contact: Emergency Medicine, General Surgery, Neurosurgery, Cardiovascular Surgery, Thoracic Surgery, Obstetrics and Gynecology, Pediatric Surgery, Urology, and Orthopedics and Traumatology. The low-exposure group comprises nine lifestyle and basic science branches: Dermatology and Venereology, Radiology, Nuclear Medicine, Medical Pathology, Medical Biochemistry, Anatomy, Histology and Embryology, Physiology, and Medical Pharmacology. The remaining 22 branches form the intermediate group. A complete listing is provided in Appendix B. Under the theoretical framework, high-exposure branches are expected to show the strongest negative association with media intensity, while low-exposure branches serve as a falsification reference.

2.2 Treatment Variable D_1 : Google News Article Count

D_1 was constructed from Google News RSS feeds queried annually using eight keyword combinations related to violence against healthcare workers in Türkiye. Three keywords were subsequently removed during preprocessing due to high noise levels — off-topic political violence, foreign news, and sexual assault coverage dominating results — leaving five treatment keywords as the final query set: "violence against doctors" (*doktora şiddet*), "assault on physicians" (*hekime saldırı*), "violence against physicians" (*hekime şiddet*)¹, "violence in hospitals" (*hastanede şiddet*), and "violence against healthcare workers" (*sağlık çalışanına şiddet*). The raw article count per year, after deduplication, serves as the primary measure of media intensity. Two alternative D_1 versions were tested — a keyword-based sentiment mean (*d1_keyword_mean*) and a BERT-based sentiment mean (*d1_bert_mean*) — but neither showed theoretical alignment with the exposure group structure. Only the raw count (*d1_count*) produced the expected directional pattern and was retained as the primary D_1 measure.

¹Two keywords target physician-directed violence using synonymous Turkish terms: *hekime şiddet* and *doktora şiddet* (both translating as 'violence against doctors/physicians'), reflecting distinct usage patterns in Turkish media where *hekim* (physician, formal register) and *doktor* (doctor, colloquial register) are not interchangeable in practice. Similarly, *hekime saldırı* captures assault-framed coverage distinct from *hekime şiddet*.

A structural limitation of Google News RSS is that each query returns at most approximately 35 results, regardless of actual article volume, introducing truncation at high-intensity years. To assess whether the truncated counts nonetheless track underlying trends, D_1 was validated against White Code annual incident notification figures over seven overlapping years, as compiled from media reports (Yılmaz, 2018; Erşan, 2022). Across the seven overlapping years where both series are available, the Spearman correlation between D_1 and White Code is $r = 0.786$ ($p = 0.036$), supporting the use of D_1 as a trend proxy while acknowledging that absolute magnitudes underestimate actual volume.

Figure 1 plots the annual trends of D_1 and D_2 over the sample period. The 2022 peak in D_1 is clearly visible, coinciding with the Ekrem Karakaya shooting. The divergence between $d2_keyword$ and $d2_annot$ after 2018 reflects the methodological transition described in Section 2.3.

Figure 1: D_1 and D_2 annual trend (2013–2025). Annual values of D_1 (Google News article count) and D_2 (Ekşi Sözlük violence flag rate). The 2022 peak in D_1 coincides with the Ekrem Karakaya shooting. D_2 (keyword) and D_2 (annot) diverge after 2018, reflecting the methodological transition described in Section 2.3.

2.3 Treatment Variable D_2 : Ekşi Sözlük Violence Discourse Index

D_2 is derived from a purposively constructed Ekşi Sözlük corpus comprising 4,148 entries across 54 threads covering the period 2013–2025. Thread selection spans five thematic categories: violence against healthcare workers, physician migration and resignation, career and specialty preferences, working conditions and salary, and health system policy. This design mirrors violence coverage within a broader context of professional deterioration rather than treating isolated incidents. The corpus is temporally skewed: 661 entries (15.9%) fall in 2013–2017, with particularly sparse coverage in 2016 ($n = 80$) and 2017 ($n = 73$), while 3,487 entries (84.1%) fall in 2018–2025. The year 2022 alone accounts for 24.5% of the full corpus ($n = 1,018$), coinciding with the Ekrem Karakaya shooting. This distributional asymmetry means that annual D_2 estimates for the pre-2018 period rest on smaller samples and carry greater measurement uncertainty.

The construction of D_2 proceeded through four stages. Prior to topic modeling,

standard text preprocessing was applied, including tokenization, stopword removal, and lemmatization; no preprocessing was applied at subsequent stages, as the few-shot LLM prompt was designed to operate on raw entry text. In the first stage, unsupervised topic modeling (LDA, BERTopic) failed to recover meaningful within-corpus structure, an unsurprising result given that the corpus was constructed around a coherent thematic domain. In the second stage, a keyword-based binary measure produced no signal in any exposure group (high-exposure $r = -0.005$, $p = 0.986$) and was dropped. In the third stage, human annotation was introduced: a subsample of 200 entries was independently coded by two annotators across three binary dimensions (physical violence, verbal violence, anti-violence sentiment), yielding inter-annotator agreement of $\kappa = 0.592$ for physical violence, $\kappa = 0.570$ for verbal violence, and $\kappa = 0.730$ for anti-violence sentiment. An entry was coded as violence-flagged if at least one violence dimension received a positive label from either annotator. In the fourth stage, the human-annotated subsample was used to construct a few-shot prompt for Claude Haiku, applied to the remaining 3,948 entries.

To empirically bound annotation uncertainty, a post-hoc validation was conducted by re-annotating the 200 human-labeled entries using the same LLM pipeline and comparing outputs against the union ground truth. Following Landis and Koch (1977), who classify $\kappa = 0.41 - 0.60$ as moderate agreement, and Artstein and Poesio (2008), who discuss acceptable thresholds for annotation tasks, LLM agreement reaches moderate levels for physical violence ($\kappa = 0.543$) and anti-violence sentiment ($\kappa = 0.583$), approaching inter-annotator agreement on the same dimensions. Agreement is lower for verbal violence ($\kappa = 0.349$) and violence normalization ($\kappa = 0.095$), reflecting task-specific subjectivity — inter-annotator agreement on violence normalization was itself low ($\kappa = 0.165$). Since the *violence_flagged* variable depends primarily on physical violence detections, moderate agreement on this dimension supports the validity of the primary measure (full agreement statistics reported in Appendix C), while the lower verbal violence agreement introduces residual uncertainty that future annotation efforts should address.

The annual proportion of violence-flagged entries ($d2_annot$) constitutes the primary D_2 measure. A severity-weighted alternative ($d2_severity$, Spearman $r = 0.929$ with $d2_annot$) was dropped due to a borderline falsification concern in the low-exposure group ($r = +0.549$, $p = 0.052$), inconsistent with a violence-specific deterrence mechanism. Table 1 summarizes the annual treatment variables.

Table 1: Year-level treatment variables ($N = 13$)

Variable	Mean	SD	Min	Max	2022
D_1 — Google News count (annual)	220.1	56.1	144	334	334 ↑
D_2 — Ekşi Sözlük flag rate (annual)	0.121	0.058	0.027	0.230	0.152

$N = 13$ annual observations (2013–2025). D_1 = raw article count from Google News RSS queries on healthcare violence keywords; D_2 = proportion of Ekşi Sözlük entries coded as violence-flagged via LLM annotation.

3. Methodology

3.1 Spearman Correlations

The analysis proceeds in three steps of increasing complexity. As a first descriptive step, Spearman rank correlations are estimated between each treatment variable and mean *score_min* separately for each exposure group, using 13 annual observations per group. The non-parametric approach is appropriate given the small sample size and the absence of distributional assumptions required by parametric alternatives. Spearman correlations cannot test whether the association differs across exposure groups in a statistically disciplined way, nor can they control for time trends or structural breaks; the year-level OLS models address both limitations.

3.2 Year-Level OLS with Exposure-Group Interactions

The primary regression is estimated at the year-group level ($N = 39$: 3 groups \times 13 years). The specification is:

$$\begin{aligned} score_min_{gt} = & \alpha + \beta_1 D_{1t} + \beta_2 (D_{1t} \times high_g) + \beta_3 (D_{1t} \times mid_g) \\ & + \beta_4 high_g + \beta_5 mid_g + \beta_6 post_reform_t + \gamma_t + \varepsilon_{gt} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where g indexes exposure group and t indexes year. $high_g$ and mid_g are binary group indicators with low-exposure as the reference. $post_reform$ is a binary indicator for 2022 and later. γ_t controls for the common time trend in two forms: year fixed effects (Y1) and a centered quadratic polynomial (Q1).

The interaction terms β_2 and β_3 are the primary coefficients of interest. The low-exposure group serves as an implicit control: if the association were driven by a general decline in TUS competitiveness, it should appear equally in low-exposure branches, and the interaction terms should be near zero.

An important identification caveat applies. D_1 and total annual TUS quota are nearly perfectly collinear (Spearman $r = +0.993$), as both series increased sharply after 2022. The year-level OLS therefore cannot fully disentangle media intensity from supply-side expansion. Specifically, the identifying variation comes from the differential timing and magnitude of score changes across exposure groups, not from separating media intensity and quota expansion as distinct forces at the year level, a separation the data do not permit. This structural limitation is addressed in the panel models below.

Standard errors are estimated using plain OLS; clustered standard errors produced unreliable inference with only three clusters. The year-level specification is estimated for D_1 only; D_2 is assessed through the branch-level panel models where its global signal is more appropriately characterized.

3.3 Panel Fixed Effects Models

As a robustness check, models are estimated at the full branch-period level ($N = 46,808$) using panel OLS with branch fixed effects and entity-clustered standard errors. Branch fixed effects μ_i absorb all time-invariant branch characteristics, such as a branch’s historical prestige or structural demand, thereby isolating within-branch variation over time. The specification is:

$$\begin{aligned} score_min_{it} = & \alpha + \beta D_t + \gamma \log(\text{quota}_{it}) \\ & + \delta_1 \text{year_c}_t + \delta_2 \text{year_c}_t^2 + \theta \text{post_reform}_t + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where i indexes branch and t indexes TUS period. D_t is either $d1_count_z$ or $d2_annot_z$, standardized to facilitate comparison. $\log(\text{quota})$ controls for supply-side expansion. Models are estimated separately for D_1 only (R1), D_2 only (R2), and both jointly (R3). Period fixed effects are not included because D_1 and D_2 vary only at the annual level. Their inclusion would create perfect collinearity with the treatment variables. The quadratic time trend absorbs the common trajectory across branches without eliminating the identifying variation in D_1 and D_2 .

4. Results

4.1 Spearman Correlations

Table 2 reports Spearman correlations between each treatment variable and mean $score_min$ by exposure group. The pattern is consistent with the theoretical prediction. D_1 shows a strong negative correlation in the high-exposure group ($r = -0.908, p < 0.001$) and a significant negative correlation in the intermediate group ($r = -0.724, p = 0.005$). The low-exposure group produces a positive and non-significant correlation ($r = +0.303, p = 0.315$). D_2 follows the same directional pattern: negative and significant in both high- ($r = -0.687, p = 0.010$) and intermediate-exposure groups ($r = -0.797, p = 0.001$), however, positive but non-significant in the low-exposure group ($r = +0.401, p = 0.174$).

The divergence between high- and low-exposure groups is the core descriptive finding. Both treatment variables behave in opposite directions across the two groups, which is inconsistent with a general downward trend in TUS scores and consistent with a group-specific deterrence mechanism². For reference, Table 2 also includes the earlier keyword-based D_2 ($d2_keyword$), which produced no signal in any group, motivating the transition to annotation-based measurement.

²For D_2 , the intermediate group produces a stronger correlation ($r = -0.797$) than the high-exposure group ($r = -0.687$). This ordering is consistent with D_2 capturing a broader professional deterioration discourse, including emigration and working conditions, rather than violence-specific exposure alone. Branches in the intermediate group may be more sensitive to this wider discursive signal. The pattern does not contradict the core finding, as both groups diverge from the low-exposure reference ($r = +0.401$).

Table 2: Spearman correlations between treatment variables and mean *score_min* by exposure group ($N = 13$ years).

Group	D_1		D_2 (annot)		D_2 (keyword)	
	r	p	r	p	r	p
High-exposure	-0.908	0.000***	-0.687	0.010**	-0.005	0.986
Intermediate	-0.724	0.005***	-0.797	0.001***	+0.055	0.859
Low-exposure	+0.303	0.315	+0.401	0.174	-0.121	0.694

Note: $*p < 0.1$, $**p < 0.05$, $***p < 0.01$. Spearman rank correlations between each treatment variable and group-year mean of *score_min*, estimated separately for each exposure group using 13 annual observations (2013–2025). D_1 = annual Google News article count for healthcare violence keywords. D_2 (annot) = annual proportion of Ekşi Sözlük entries coded as violence-flagged via LLM annotation (primary measure). D_2 (keyword) = legacy keyword-based binary measure, included for comparison. A negative correlation indicates that higher media intensity is associated with lower branch minimum scores, interpreted as declining specialty attractiveness.

Figure 2 illustrates the divergence in mean *score_min* trajectories across exposure groups over the full sample period. High- and intermediate-exposure branches move together in the pre-2022 period before declining sharply, while low-exposure branches rise after 2022, a pattern consistent with the Spearman correlations reported above.

Figure 2: Parallel trends — mean *score_min* by exposure group. Mean branch-level minimum TUS scores averaged across spring and autumn periods (2013–2025). Vertical dashed line marks 2022. High- and intermediate-exposure branches decline after 2022 while low-exposure branches rise, consistent with a group-specific deterrence pattern.

4.2 Year-Level OLS: Primary Results

Table 3 reports the year-level OLS results. Although the Spearman correlations established that a negative association exists in high- and intermediate-exposure groups, they are unable to test whether this difference across groups is statistically meaningful once a common time trend is accounted for. The OLS interaction terms address this directly. They ask whether D_1 is more negatively associated with scores in high- and intermediate-exposure branches than in the low-exposure reference group, controlling for shared trends

and the 2022 structural break. The interaction coefficients are the primary object of interest. Under both the quadratic trend (Q1) and year dummy (Y1) specifications, the interaction terms are identical: $D_1 \times \text{high} = -0.965$ ($p = 0.002$) and $D_1 \times \text{mid} = -0.849$ ($p = 0.005$). Both effects are significant at the 1% level and stable across specifications.

The D_1 main effect, which captures the association in the low-exposure reference group, behaves differently. Under the quadratic specification it is positive and significant (+1.048, $p = 0.037$). Nonetheless, under the year dummy specification, it is negative and significant (-5.562 , $p < 0.001$). This signreversal elucidates that the main effect cannot be separately identified from the time trend and should not be interpreted as a standalone finding. The primary finding rests entirely on the interaction terms, which are unaffected by this instability.

Table 3: Year-level OLS results ($N = 39$)

Variable	Q1 Coef.	Q1 SE	Q1 p	Y1 Coef.	Y1 SE	Y1 p	Note
D_1 main effect	+1.048	0.481	0.037**	-5.562	0.296	0.000***	Low-exp ref
$D_1 \times \text{high}$	-0.965	0.279	0.002***	-0.965	0.274	0.002***	Identical
$D_1 \times \text{mid}$	-0.849	0.279	0.005***	-0.849	0.274	0.005***	Identical
$R^2 = 0.981$ (Q1), 0.986 (Y1)							

Note: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Dependent variable: group-year mean of *score_min* (branch-level minimum TUS score). *high_exp* and *mid_exp* are binary group indicators; *post_reform* = 1 for 2022 and later. $N = 39$ (3 exposure groups \times 13 years). Plain OLS; clustered SE not used due to only 3 clusters. A combined specification including both D_1 and D_2 interaction terms yields an identical pattern for D_1 interactions; the D_2 main effect is significant under year dummies (coef = -0.679 , SE = 0.231 , $p = 0.008$) but D_2 interaction terms are not, confirming that D_2 captures a global rather than group-specific association. Full coefficient estimates including control variables reported in Appendix D.

4.3 Outlier Analysis and Leave-One-Out Sensitivity

The D_1 main effect instability prompted an investigation of whether any single year was driving the result. A z-score analysis flagged 2022 as the only year exceeding a z-score of 2.0 ($z = 2.03$). It also coincides with the Ekrem Karakaya shooting, the most high-profile healthcare violence incident in the sample period, and the year D_1 reached its peak value of 334 articles. However, 2022 is also theoretically the most important year in the sample, and excluding it on statistical grounds alone would be circular.

Therefore, a leave-one-out analysis was conducted, dropping each year in turn and re-estimating the primary quadratic specification, and it is confirmed that interaction coefficients remain significant at the 1% level across all 13 iterations. When 2022 is excluded, the interaction terms are if anything slightly larger in magnitude ($D_1 \times \text{high} = -1.018$, $D_1 \times \text{mid} = -1.051$) and remain highly significant ($p = 0.001$ for both). This confirms that no single year, including the theoretically pivotal 2022, drives the interaction findings. The D_1 main effect instability persists across all iterations. It is attributable to trend-control identification rather than any influential observation. Full leave-one-out results are reported in Appendix A.

4.4 Panel Fixed Effects: Robustness

Table 4 reports results from the branch-level panel models. The D1-only model (R1) produces a positive coefficient for $d1_count_z$ (+0.526, $p = 0.035$), a result that appears inconsistent with the negative associations found in the year-level models. This reversal reflects a structural difference between the two model designs. The year-level OLS identifies the differential effect of D_1 across exposure groups through interaction terms. It asks whether D_1 is more negatively associated with scores in high-exposure branches than in low-exposure branches. Nevertheless, the panel model estimates a single global coefficient for D_1 across all branches simultaneously, without group differentiation. In years when D_1 is high, low-exposure branches, where the association is positive, pull the global coefficient upward by offsetting the negative signal from high-exposure branches. The positive R1 coefficient therefore reflects the aggregation of opposing group-specific effects, not a contradiction of the year-level findings. This interpretation is consistent with the Spearman results in Table 2, where D_1 is positive in the low-exposure group ($r = +0.303$) and strongly negative in the high-exposure group ($r = -0.908$).

The D2-only model (R2) tells a different story. $d2_annot_z$ shows a strong global negative association with $score_min$ across all branches (-0.403 , $p < 0.001$). It is a pattern that does not mirror the group-specific structure found for D_1 . By the validation framework of Grimmer and Stewart (2013), D_1 has stronger alignment with the specific hypothesis, while D_2 captures a broader index of professional deterioration. This divergence is discussed further in Section 5.2. Table 5 confirms that D2 signal is robust to the inclusion of $\log(\text{quota})$.

In the joint model (R3), D_1 becomes insignificant (+0.106, $p = 0.616$) while D2 retains full significance (-0.389 , $p < 0.001$). The annual Spearman correlation between D_1 and D_2 is $r = +0.542$. Although it is a moderate result, still not high enough to attribute this pattern to collinearity alone. A more plausible interpretation is that D_2 absorbs the within-branch time-series variation that D_1 also partially captures, leaving D_1 with no independent explanatory contribution in the joint specification. This pattern supports treating D_1 and D_2 as separate primary models rather than a combined specification, and reinforces the year-level OLS as the appropriate framework for testing the group-specific hypothesis.

As a further sensitivity check, $\log(\text{quota})$ is added to each specification. Despite near-perfect annual collinearity between D_1 and quota at the annual level (Spearman $r = +0.993$), the panel structure separates their within-branch signals: D_1 remains significant

Table 4: Panel OLS — branch FE, without $\log(\text{quota})$ ($N = 46,808$)

Variable	R1: D_1 only	R2: D_2 only	R3: $D_1 + D_2$
$d1_count_z$	+0.526** (0.213)	—	+0.106 (0.219)
$d2_annot_z$	—	-0.403*** (0.063)	-0.389*** (0.062)
$post_reform$	-2.433*** (0.682)	-0.842* (0.429)	-1.061 (0.669)
R^2 (within)	0.036	0.040	0.040

Note: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Standard errors in parentheses. Dependent variable: branch-period minimum TUS score. Branch fixed effects with entity-clustered SE (≈ 40 clusters). D_1 and D_2 z-scored. R1 produces a positive D_1 coefficient because the global estimate aggregates opposing group-specific effects — see Section 4.4.

in the D_1 -only specification (+0.642, $p = 0.001$), showing that D_1 carries signal beyond supply-side quota movements. D_2 is robust to $\log(\text{quota})$ inclusion across all specifications, with the coefficient remaining stable and significant ($d2_annot_z = -0.377$ in S2, -0.342 in S3).

Table 5: Panel OLS — branch FE, with $\log(\text{quota})$ ($N = 46,808$)

Variable	S1: $D_1 + \text{quota}$	S2: $D_2 + \text{quota}$	S3: $D_1 + D_2 + \text{quota}$
$d1_count_z$	+0.642*** (0.201)	—	+0.272 (0.206)
$d2_annot_z$	—	-0.377*** (0.061)	-0.342*** (0.064)
$\log(\text{quota})$	-1.724*** (0.297)	-1.685*** (0.302)	-1.695*** (0.302)
$post_reform$	-1.804*** (0.647)	-0.053 (0.400)	-0.610 (0.620)
R^2 (within)	0.060	0.063	0.063

Note: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Standard errors in parentheses. Dependent variable: branch-period minimum TUS score. Branch fixed effects with entity-clustered SE (≈ 40 clusters). D_1 and D_2 z-scored. $\log(\text{quota})$ included to test whether D_1 signal persists beyond supply-side expansion. Annual Spearman $r(D_1, \log(\text{quota})) = +0.993$; signals remain separable within panel structure.

5. Discussion

5.1 Summary of Findings

The results provide consistent correlational evidence that higher media intensity is associated with declining attractiveness in high- and intermediate-exposure branches, while low-exposure branches show no such pattern. This group-specific structure holds across Spearman correlations, year-level OLS interaction terms, and panel fixed effects models. Moreover, it is robust to leave-one-out sensitivity analysis including the theoretically pivotal year 2022.

5.2 Interpretation

The interaction terms remain stable across both trend specifications. $D_1 \times \text{high}$ and $D_1 \times \text{mid}$ are identical under quadratic and year dummy controls despite the D_1 main effect changing sign between the two, suggesting the differential effect is identified from

within-period variation in the relative standing of branches rather than from the overall level of D_1 .

The group-specific pattern is also theoretically informative. If the observed score declines reflected a general deterioration in TUS competitiveness, driven by, for instance, the 2022 physician salary reform or accelerating emigration trends documented by Eser et al. (2024), one would expect a uniform downward shift across all branches. Instead, low-exposure branches show stable or rising scores. High-exposure branches declined by 1.35 points on average after 2022, while low-exposure branches rose by 0.88 points. This asymmetry is consistent with a mechanism in which violence coverage selectively deters candidates from branches perceived as high-risk. It is also consistent with the broader literature on information and career choice. For instance, Tek Sevindik et al. (2025) document that healthcare violence coverage shapes professional perceptions among nursing students, and Bo et al. (2020) show that media intensity of anti-doctor violence reduces medicine enrollment in China. The present findings suggest that a similar dynamic may operate at the specialty level among physicians already committed to a medical career.

The two treatment variables tell partially different stories. D_1 , as a measure of mainstream media intensity, more cleanly captures violence as a career-relevant signal. By the validation framework of Grimmer and Stewart (2013), which requires that a text measure captures what it is theoretically intended to capture, D_1 has stronger alignment with the specific hypothesis under examination. D_2 , derived from Ekşi Sözlük, captures a broader discursive environment including physician emigration, working conditions, and salary grievances, which may explain why its panel signal is global rather than group-specific. If D_2 indeed represents general deterioration in the health system rather than violence-specific deterrence, its global pattern is not merely a measurement issue but an empirically informative finding in its own right. It indicates that system-level professional discontent may influence specialty attractiveness independently of exposure to violence. A more tightly focused thread selection could recover the group-specific pattern while preserving the annotation pipeline developed here as a methodological foundation.

5.3 Limitations

Several limitations bound the interpretation. First, the year-level identification rests on 13 effective treatment observations despite the large branch-period panel. The treatment variables D_1 and D_2 vary only annually, meaning that the identifying variation in the primary OLS models is limited to 13 data points per group. The year dummy specification compounds this by consuming 12 degrees of freedom on a sample of $N = 39$, leaving little residual variation for precise estimation. The interaction findings are robust, yet the statistical power available to detect smaller effects is limited.

Second, D_1 and total annual quota are nearly perfectly collinear at the annual level

(Spearman $r = +0.993$); the year-level models cannot fully disentangle media intensity from supply-side expansion. Figure 3 illustrates this co-movement: all three exposure groups spike sharply in 2022, mirroring the D_1 peak. The parallel movement across groups suggests that quota expansion was a system-wide phenomenon rather than exposure-group specific, supporting its inclusion as a control variable in the panel models.

Figure 3: Quota trend by exposure group. Mean quota count per branch by exposure group (left) and total annual quota alongside D_1 and D_2 (right), 2013–2025. The sharp post-2022 increase across all groups mirrors the D_1 spike, illustrating near-perfect annual collinearity (Spearman $r = +0.993$).

Third, the D_1 main effect is unstable across trend specifications, changing sign between the quadratic and year dummy models. This instability is attributable to trend-control identification rather than influential observations, as confirmed by the leave-one-out analysis, but it prevents any standalone interpretation of D_1 's effect on low-exposure branches.

Fourth, the Ekşi Sözlük corpus was constructed purposively, limiting its generalizability as a measure of general public discourse. The platform also skews toward educated, urban users, which partially overlaps with the TUS candidate population but does not fully represent it.

Fifth, the LLM annotation extension applies Claude Haiku to 3,948 entries based on a few-shot prompt derived from 200 human-labeled examples. The post-hoc validation reported in Section 2.3 shows moderate agreement on the primary violence dimension ($\kappa = 0.543$), approaching inter-annotator agreement on the same dimension ($\kappa = 0.592$); lower agreement on verbal violence ($\kappa = 0.349$) introduces residual uncertainty that future annotation efforts should address.

More fundamentally, these results are correlational. The absence of a credible exogenous instrument for media intensity, and the inability to rule out confounding by system-wide shocks such as the 2022 salary reform, means that no causal claim can be made. The group-specific pattern is consistent with a deterrence mechanism, but it is also consistent with other explanations, including differential responses to non-media factors that happen to correlate with exposure group classification.

6. Conclusion

This study examined whether the intensity of healthcare violence coverage in Turkish media and online discourse is associated with shifts in medical specialty preferences, as measured by branch-level minimum scores on the TUS. The evidence consistently points in the same direction. Higher media intensity is associated with declining minimum scores in high- and intermediate-exposure branches, while low-exposure branches remain unaffected. This group-specific pattern holds across non-parametric correlations, year-level OLS interaction terms, and branch-level panel fixed effects models, and survives leave-one-out sensitivity analysis.

The methodological contribution lies in the construction of D_2 . The annotation pipeline — moving from failed unsupervised topic modeling through keyword scoring to human annotation and LLM-based corpus extension, with a post-hoc validation yielding moderate agreement on primary violence dimensions ($\kappa = 0.543$ for physical violence against union ground truth) — illustrates both the potential and the limits of automated text processing for longitudinal social science measurement. The final measure is theoretically grounded, reproducible, and shows stronger signal than its keyword-based predecessor. Still, its global rather than group-specific behavior in panel models raises questions about what exactly it captures beyond violence-specific discourse.

Taken together, the findings extend the Bo et al. (2020) framework to a new institutional context and a different career decision point. They suggest that sustained media coverage of workplace violence may reshape revealed specialty preferences among physicians, independently of the direct experience of violence. Whether this association reflects a genuine information or deterrence mechanism, or is partly driven by correlated system-level shocks, remains an open question that future work with richer identification strategies could address. A natural next step would be to exploit geographic or specialty-level variation in actual violence exposure, rather than relying solely on national media intensity, to more precisely identify the mechanism linking coverage to career decisions. In the meantime, the consistency of the group-specific pattern across multiple specifications suggests that media coverage of healthcare violence is not merely a symptom of systemic deterioration.

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Appendices

A. Leave-One-Out Sensitivity — Quadratic Specification

Table 6: Leave-one-out sensitivity. Interaction coefficients significant at the 1% level across all 13 iterations. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Dropped	N	D_1 main effect	$D_1 \times$ high	$D_1 \times$ mid
BASELINE	39	+1.048** (0.037)	-0.965*** (0.002)	-0.849*** (0.005)
2013	36	+1.390*** (0.003)	-1.147*** (0.000)	-1.093*** (0.000)
2014	36	+0.914* (0.084)	-0.902*** (0.006)	-0.820** (0.012)
2015	36	+0.985* (0.061)	-0.946*** (0.004)	-0.807** (0.011)
2016	36	+1.100** (0.024)	-0.940*** (0.002)	-0.805*** (0.006)
2017	36	+1.034** (0.049)	-0.918*** (0.004)	-0.801*** (0.010)
2018	36	+1.064** (0.039)	-0.966*** (0.002)	-0.842*** (0.006)
2019	36	+1.075** (0.049)	-1.001*** (0.003)	-0.876*** (0.007)
2020	36	+1.096** (0.045)	-1.006*** (0.003)	-0.886*** (0.007)
2021	36	+1.161** (0.035)	-1.009*** (0.002)	-0.886*** (0.007)
2022	36	+2.013*** (0.009)	-1.018*** (0.001)	-1.051*** (0.001)
2023	36	+0.841 (0.171)	-0.913*** (0.006)	-0.773** (0.017)
2024	36	+1.008* (0.090)	-0.995*** (0.003)	-0.795** (0.014)
2025	36	+0.431 (0.377)	-0.758*** (0.008)	-0.610** (0.028)

B. Branch Classification by Exposure Group

Table 7: TUS branches and exposure group classification adapting the controllable lifestyle framework of Dorsey et al. (2003) to the Turkish specialty context. Turkish branch names in parentheses.

Branch	Group
<i>High-exposure — surgical/emergency (n = 9)</i>	
Emergency Medicine (<i>Acil Tıp</i>)	High
General Surgery (<i>Genel Cerrahi</i>)	High
Neurosurgery (<i>Beyin ve Sinir Cerrahisi</i>)	High
Cardiovascular Surgery (<i>Kalp ve Damar Cerrahisi</i>)	High
Thoracic Surgery (<i>Göğüs Cerrahisi</i>)	High
Obstetrics and Gynecology (<i>Kadın Hastalıkları ve Doğum</i>)	High
Pediatric Surgery (<i>Çocuk Cerrahisi</i>)	High
Urology (<i>Üroloji</i>)	High
Orthopedics and Traumatology (<i>Ortopedi ve Travmatoloji</i>)	High
<i>Intermediate (n = 22)</i>	
Internal Medicine (<i>İç Hastalıkları</i>)	Intermediate
Psychiatry (<i>Ruh Sağlığı ve Hastalıkları</i>)	Intermediate
Ophthalmology (<i>Göz Hastalıkları</i>)	Intermediate

Branch	Group
Otolaryngology (<i>Kulak Burun Boğaz Hastalıkları</i>)	Intermediate
Pediatrics (<i>Çocuk Sağlığı ve Hastalıkları</i>)	Intermediate
Child and Adolescent Psychiatry (<i>Çocuk ve Ergen Ruh Sağlığı ve Hastalıkları</i>)	Intermediate
Infectious Diseases (<i>Enfeksiyon Hastalıkları ve Klinik Mikrobiyoloji</i>)	Intermediate
Cardiology (<i>Kardiyoloji</i>)	Intermediate
Neurology (<i>Nöroloji</i>)	Intermediate
Pulmonology (<i>Göğüs Hastalıkları</i>)	Intermediate
Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation (<i>Fiziksel Tıp ve Rehabilitasyon</i>)	Intermediate
Anesthesiology and Reanimation (<i>Anesteziyoloji ve Reanimasyon</i>)	Intermediate
Radiation Oncology (<i>Radyasyon Onkolojisi</i>)	Intermediate
Family Medicine (<i>Aile Hekimliği</i>)	Intermediate
Public Health (<i>Halk Sağlığı</i>)	Intermediate
Medical Microbiology (<i>Tıbbi Mikrobiyoloji</i>)	Intermediate
Medical Genetics (<i>Tıbbi Genetik</i>)	Intermediate
Sports Medicine (<i>Spor Hekimliği</i>)	Intermediate
Forensic Medicine (<i>Adli Tıp</i>)	Intermediate
Undersea and Hyperbaric Medicine (<i>Sualtı Hekimliği ve Hiperbarik Tıp</i>)	Intermediate
Medical Ecology and Hydroclimatology (<i>Tıbbi Ekoloji ve Hidroklimatoloji</i>)	Intermediate
Aviation and Space Medicine (<i>Hava ve Uzay Hekimliği</i>)	Intermediate
<i>Low-exposure — lifestyle/basic science (n = 9)</i>	
Dermatology and Venereology (<i>Deri ve Zührevi Hastalıkları</i>)	Low
Radiology (<i>Radyoloji</i>)	Low
Nuclear Medicine (<i>Nükleer Tıp</i>)	Low
Medical Pathology (<i>Tıbbi Patoloji</i>)	Low
Medical Biochemistry (<i>Tıbbi Biyokimya</i>)	Low
Anatomy (<i>Anatomi</i>)	Low
Histology and Embryology (<i>Histoloji ve Embriyoloji</i>)	Low
Physiology (<i>Fizyoloji</i>)	Low
Medical Pharmacology (<i>Tıbbi Farmakoloji</i>)	Low
<i>Note: Plastic, Reconstructive and Aesthetic Surgery excluded due to atypical demand structure.</i>	

C. LLM Annotation Validation — Agreement Statistics

Table 8 reports Cohen’s κ between LLM labels and each human annotator, as well as the union ground truth, across all five annotation dimensions. The union ground truth assigns a positive label if either human annotator coded the dimension as positive.

Table 8: LLM–human agreement (Cohen’s κ) across annotation dimensions. Union ground truth = positive label from either annotator. Inter-annotator κ included for reference.

Dimension	vs Annotator 1	vs Annotator 2	vs Union	Inter-annotator
physical_violence	0.481	0.513	0.543	0.592
verbal_violence	0.332	0.211	0.349	0.570
anti_violence	0.539	0.566	0.583	0.730
violence_normalized	0.158	0.108	0.095	0.165
sarcasm	0.255	0.376	0.415	0.321

The *violence_flagged* variable used to construct D_2 depends on positive labels in *physical_violence* or *verbal_violence* from either annotator. LLM agreement on *physical_violence* ($\kappa = 0.543$ vs union) approaches inter-annotator agreement ($\kappa = 0.592$), supporting the validity of the primary measure. Agreement on *violence_normalized* is low for both LLM–human ($\kappa = 0.095$) and inter-annotator comparisons ($\kappa = 0.165$), indicating task-specific subjectivity rather than model failure.

D. Full Coefficient Estimates — Year-Level OLS

Table 9: Year-level OLS — Full coefficient estimates ($N = 39$)

Variable	Q1 Coef.	Q1 SE	Q1 p	Y1 Coef.	Y1 SE	Y1 p	Note
D_1 main effect	+1.048	0.481	0.037**	−5.562	0.296	0.000***	Low-exp ref
$D_1 \times$ high	−0.965	0.279	0.002***	−0.965	0.274	0.002***	Identical
$D_1 \times$ mid	−0.849	0.279	0.005***	−0.849	0.274	0.005***	Identical
<i>high_exp</i>	−10.835	0.284	0.000***	−10.835	0.279	0.000***	
<i>mid_exp</i>	−4.370	0.284	0.000***	−4.370	0.279	0.000***	
<i>post_reform</i>	−2.350	1.008	0.027**	+12.322	0.272	0.000***	†
<i>year_c</i>	+0.116	0.076	0.141	—	—	—	
<i>year_c</i> ²	+0.046	0.018	0.015**	—	—	—	
Intercept	+65.114	0.299	0.000***	+55.922	0.178	0.000***	

$R^2 = 0.981$ (Q1), 0.986 (Y1)

Note: * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. Q1 = quadratic trend specification; Y1 = year dummy specification. Low-exposure = reference group. $N = 39$ (3 exposure groups \times 13 years). Plain OLS; clustered SE not used due to only 3 clusters. Year dummy coefficients for Y1 not reported; 12 year indicators included. † *post_reform* in Y1 overlaps with year dummies; coefficient is not directly interpretable.